

Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology

Department of Mechanical Engineering

Report On A Design Of Shell and Tube Heat Exchanger

Course No: ME 310

Course Title: Thermo Fluid Design System

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1 INTRODUCTION TO HEAT EXCHANGER

A heat exchanger is a device that transfers heat between two fluids or more. In some cases, a solid wall prevents the fluid from mixing with one another. In other cases, the fluids may be in direct contact with one another. In case of most efficient heat exchanger, the surface area of the wall between the fluids is maximized while at the same time the fluid flow resistance is minimized. Fins are sometimes used to increase the effective surface area in order to increase heat transfer and also to induce turbulence. Heat exchangers are commonly used in air conditioning, refrigerator, space heating, power stations, chemical plants, petrochemical plants, petroleum refineries, natural-gas processing and sewage treatment. Probable the most commonly known heat exchanger is a car radiator. In a radiator, a fluid known as engine coolant flows through the radiator and cool air is blown over the surface of radiator. As a result, the radiator is cooled down and air is heated. There are primarily three types of flow arrangements with heat exchangers:

- i. Parallel Flow: Both fluids come in from the same side, move parallel to each other as they flow to the other side.
- ii. Counter Flow: The fluids enter from opposite sides and move parallel to each other. Generally counter flow ensures the most heat transfer making it the most efficient design.
- iii. Cross Flow: Both fluids move perpendicular to each other. If these fluids mix with each other, it's called mixed type cross flow. Otherwise, it's known as unmixed.

1.1 FUNCTIONS OF HEAT EXCHANGER

A heat exchanger is used for different purposes. Some of them are:

- i. To reduce the temperature of a hot fluid by means of a cooler fluid
- ii. To increase the temperature of a cool fluid by means of a hot fluid
- iii. To boil a liquid while condensing a hotter gaseous fluid
- iv. To condense a gaseous fluid by means of a cooler fluid
- v. To boil a liquid by means of a hotter fluid

Whatever role the heat exchanger fulfills, to transfer heat in between fluids, there must be a temperature difference in between the fluids involved. Both fluids must come into thermal contact. Naturally, heat can flow only from the hotter to the cooler fluid.

2 CLASSIFICATION OF HEAT EXCHANGER

Heat exchangers are designed in so many sizes, types, configurations and flow arrangements and used for so many purposes that they can be classified in different groups, such as:

- ✚ According to heat transfer process
- ✚ According to the flow arrangement
- ✚ According to the construction

2.1 ACCORDING TO HEAT TRANSFER PROCESS

- i. **DIRECT CONTACT TYPE:** Two immiscible fluids at different temperature come in direct contact with each other to transfer heat. Cooling towers, jet condensers etc. are best examples of this type.
- ii. **RECUPERATOR (OR) TRANSFER TYPE HEAT EXCHANGER:** Both hot and cold fluids flow simultaneously through the device and they are separated by a flat wall or curved surface. They are mostly used in engineering fields. For example, oil coolers, air preheaters, economizers, radiators etc. are well known.
- iii. **REGENERATIVE (OR) STORAGE TYPE HEAT EXCHANGER:** In this case, both hot and cold fluid flow alternatively at the same surface. When hot fluid flows over the surface in an interval of time, the surface receives heat from the hot fluid and increases its internal energy. When cold fluid flows over this hot surface in the next interval of time, stored energy is transferred to this cold fluid. It is used in internal combustion engine and gas turbines.

2.2 ACCORDING TO FLOW ARRANGEMENT

- i. **PARALLEL FLOW:** Both fluids come in from the same side, move parallel to each other as they flow to the other side.
- ii. **COUNTER FLOW:** The fluids enter from opposite sides and move parallel to each other. Generally counter flow ensures the most heat transfer making it the most efficient design.
- iii. **CROSS FLOW:** Both fluids move perpendicular to each other. If these fluids mix with each other, it's called mixed type cross flow. Otherwise, it's known as unmixed.

Fig: (a) Parallel Flow, (b) Counter Flow, (c) Cross Flow

2.3 ACCORDING TO CONSTRUCTIONAL FEATURES

- i. **TUBULAR HEAT EXCHANGER:** These are also called tube in tube or concentric tube or double pipe heat exchanger. These are widely used in many sizes and different flow arrangement and type.

Fig: Tubular Heat Exchanger

- ii. **SHELL AND TUBE HEAT EXCHANGER:** It is made of a shell and a large number of parallel tubes housing in it. One fluid flows inside the tube and the other flows outside the tubes through the shell. It has large surface area in a small volume and can be classified in different types.

Fig: Shell and Tube Heat Exchanger

- iii. **FINNED TYPE HEAT EXCHANGER:** When heat transfer rate is quite high, the extruded surfaces are used on the one side of the heat exchanger. Fins are always added on the gas side. These types are used in gas turbines, automobiles, aero planes etc.
- iv. **COMPACT HEAT EXCHANGER:** Area density is the ratio of heat transfer surface area to the volume. A heat exchanger with an area density greater than $700 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$ is called compact heat exchanger. These are usually cross flow. For example, automobile radiators have an area density in order of 1100.

Fig: Compact heat exchanger

2.4 ACCORDING TO PHYSICAL STATE OF FLUIDS:

- i. **CONDENSERS:** In this type, condensing fluid remains at a constant temperature while the temperature of the cold fluid gradually increases. That means hot fluid losses latent heat and part of which is received by the cold fluid.
- ii. **EVAPORATORS:** In this type, the boiling fluid remains at constant temperature while hot fluid gradually loses its temperature. That means the hot fluid loses its energy and part of it is received by the cold fluid as latent heat.

Fig: Temp profile of Condenser and Evaporation Heat Exchanger

3 Introduction to Shell and Tube Heat Exchanger

Shell and tube heat exchanger is one of the most popular class of heat exchanger designs. It is mostly used in oil refineries and other large chemical process. It is suited for high pressure applications. As the name implies, it is consisted of a large shell and a bundle of tube inside this shell. The shell actually works as a large pressure vessel. Two fluids flow at a time, one flows through the tubes and the other flows over the tubes or through the shell to transfer heat between the two fluids. The tube set is known as tube bundle, and can be composed of several types of tubes, such as plain, longitudinally finned etc.

Shell and tube heat exchangers are generally used for applications where pressure is greater 30 bar and temperature is higher than 260°C. This is possible because of their robust shape. Two fluids of different temperatures flow through the heat exchanger. One fluid flows through the tubes, known as tube side fluid, and the other, known as shell side fluid, flows trough the shell. Heat is transferred from one fluid to the other tube walls, either from shell side to tube side or tube side to shell side. The fluids can be either liquids or gases on either the shell or the tube side. To transfer heat efficiently, heat transfer area should be large, leading to the use of many tubes. Waste heat can be put to use in this way. This is an efficient way to conserve energy.

3.1 Basic Components of Shell and Tube Heat Exchanger

- **Shell and Shell Side Nozzle:** The shell is the container for the shell side fluid. The nozzles are the inlet and outlet exit ports. The shell is normally of circular cross section and made of steel.
- **Tubes:** The tubes are the basic component of shell and tube heat exchanger. They provide the surface area to transfer heat between one fluid and the other. The tubes may be seamless or welded. They are mostly made of copper or steel alloys.
- **Tube Sheets:** It is a single round plate of metal. This plate is drilled and grooved to take the tubes, the gaskets, the spacer rods and the bolt circle where it is fastened to the shell. The tubes are held in place by this sheet.
- **Tube Side Channels and Nozzles:** These channels and nozzles control the flow of the tube side fluid in to and out of the tubes of the exchanger. Since the tube side fluid is generally the more corrosive, these channels and nozzles will often be made out of alloy materials.
- **Tube Layout Pattern:** Normally four types of tube layout pattern are used. They are triangular (30 degree), rotated triangular (60 degree), square (90 degree), and rotated square (45 degree).

- **Channel Covers:** These covers are round plates. They are bolted to the channel flanges and can be removed for tube inspection without disturbing the tube side piping. Bonnets with flanged nozzles or threaded connections for the tube side piping are often used instead of channels and channel covers in smaller heat exchangers.
- **Baffles:** Baffles support the tubes in the proper position during assembly and operation. They prevent vibration of tubes caused by flow induces eddies. They also guide the shell side flow back and forth and across the tube field. This increases the velocity of the fluid and the heat transfer coefficient also increases.

Fig: Shell and Tube heat exchanger with different components

3.2 Classification of Shell and Tube Heat Exchanger

Shell and tube heat exchanger can be classified in two different methods, such as:

- i. According to the construction
- ii. According to the flow arrangement

3.2.1 According to the Construction

- I. Fixed type heat exchanger
- II. U-tube type heat exchanger
- III. Floating head type heat exchanger

I. Fixed Type Heat Exchanger:

This type heat exchangers have straight tubes. These tubes are secured at both ends to tube sheets welded to the shell. In this construction, channel covers can be made removable (AEL), bonnet-type channel covers (BEM) or integral tube sheets (NEN). This type of heat exchanger is very simple to construct, so it is less costly. Cost effectiveness is the principal advantage of this type. The tube bundle is fixed to the shell and cannot be removed. So, the outsides of these tubes cannot be cleaned mechanically. It is a big disadvantage of this type.

Fig; Fixed Type Heat Exchanger

II. U-Tube Heat Exchanger:

The tubes of this type heat exchanger are bent in the shape of a U. In a U-tube heat exchanger, only one tube sheet is present. Though the cost of the single tube sheet is low, but the cost incurred for the bending of the tubes and the larger shell diameter make it comparable to that of a fixed tube sheet exchanger.

One end of the U-tube is free, so the bundle can expand or contract in response to stress differentials. Also, as the tube bundle can be removed, the outsides of the tubes can be cleaned. But the insides of the tubes cannot be cleaned easily. So, this type of heat exchanger should not be used for services with a dirty fluid inside tube.

Fig: U-Tube Type Heat Exchanger

III. Floating Type Heat Exchanger:

This type of design is the most versatile and costliest Shell and Tube Heat Exchanger (STHE). One tube sheet is fixed relative to the shell and the other is free to float within the shell. As a result, tube bundle can expand freely and cleaning of both insides and outsides of the tubes is easier. So, it can be used where both shell side fluid and tube side fluid are dirty. So, it is widely used in petroleum refineries.

Fig: Floating Type Heat Exchanger

3.2.2 According to Flow

This can be of various types based on how many passes are present in the shell and in the tubes.

- A heat exchanger with one 'U' turn of tubes in the shell is called one shell pass and two tube pass. Tube fluid enters from one side of tube and leaves from the other. The shell fluid enters from one side and leaves from the opposite side.
- A heat exchanger with two passes in the shell and four passes in the tubes is called two shell pass and four tubes pass.

In this way a heat exchanger can be of 2,4,6... shell pass and 2,4,6,8... tube pass. They are called according to the number of shell and tubes they pass.

Fig: One Shell Pass and Two Tube Pass

Fig: Two Shell Pass and Four Tube Pass

4 Problem and Calculation

70,000 Kg/h of kerosene will be heated from 25 to 50°C by cooling a gasoline stream from 70 to 50 °C. Inlet pressure will be 400 KPa for each stream and the maximum pressure drop of 70 KPa for kerosene and 50 KPa for gasoline are permissible. Assume suitable fouling factors for this application. Design a shell and tube heat exchanger.

Given, 1) 1" OD tubes (14BWG) on 1¼" square pitch (PT)

2) Fixed tube plate type

3) Tube ID=0.834"

4) 1 shell pass-8tube pass

Design for suitable tube length. The final report will include material selection, economical analysis (both hand and software analyses), thermo-hydraulic calculations (both hand and software), mechanical design, and technical drawings of the components and the assembly.

Given Data

		Tube	Shell
Fluid Name		Kerosene (cold fluid)	n-Octane (hot fluid)
Mass flow Rate , \dot{m} (kg/s)		19.44	-
Inlet Temperature , T_i (°C)		25	70
Outlet Temperature , T_o (°C)		50	50
Square Pitch , PT inch (mm)		1¼" (31.75)	-
14 BWG	Outer Tube Diameter , inch (mm)	1" (25.4)	-
	Inner Tube Diameter , inch (mm)	0.834" (21.18)	-
Maximum Pressure Drop (KPa)		70	50
Inlet Pressure (KPa)		400	

$$(T_{avg})_{tube} = \frac{70+50}{2}$$

$$= 60^{\circ}\text{C}$$

$$(T_{avg})_{shell} = \frac{50+25}{2}$$

$$= 37.5^{\circ}\text{C}$$

$$\rho_t = 683.605 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

$$\rho_s = 796.57 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

$$\mu_t = 0.3551 \times 10^{-3} \text{ Ns/m}^2$$

$$\mu_s = 1.22 \times 10^{-3} \text{ Ns/m}^2$$

$$C_p = 2.323 \times 10^3 \text{ J/KgK}$$

$$C_p = 2.03 \times 10^3 \text{ J/KgK}$$

$$K_t = 0.11885 \text{ W/mk}$$

$$K_t = 0.13 \text{ W/mk}$$

$$Pr = 4$$

$$Pr = 15$$

*** All the fluid properties are at Average Temperature

Total Tube Cross Section Area Calculation, A_t :

$$\dot{m}_h = \rho_t \times A_t \times u_t \text{ (Let , } u_t = 1.48 \text{ms}^{-1}\text{)}$$

$$\text{or, } 27.8 = 683.605 \times A_t \times 1.48$$

$$\text{or, } A_t = 0.027 \text{ m}^2$$

Number Of Total Tube, N_t :

$$A_t = (N_t / N_p) \times \pi / 4 \times ID^2$$

$$\text{or, } 0.027 = \frac{N_t}{8} \times \frac{\pi}{4} \times (0.02118)^2$$

$$\text{or, } N_t = 613$$

$$\text{or, } N_t \approx 650$$

Heat Transfer Rate (Q) & Mass Flow Rate Of Hot Fluid (\dot{m}_h) :

$$Q = \dot{m}_c (C_p) (T_{c,o} - T_{c,i}) = \dot{m}_h (C_p)_h (T_{h,o} - T_{h,i})$$

$$\text{or, } Q = 19.44 \times 2.323 \times 10^3 \times (50 - 25) = \dot{m}_h \times 2.03 \times 10^3 \times (70 - 50)$$

$$\text{or, } \dot{m}_h = 27.8 \text{ kg/s}$$

$$\text{or, } Q = 1128.978 \times 10^3 \text{ W}$$

LMTD:

$$\Delta T_{LM} = \frac{(70-50)-(50-25)}{\ln\left(\frac{70-50}{50-25}\right)}$$
$$= 22.41^\circ\text{C}$$

Fig: Temperature Profile

Total Outside Tube Area, A_o :

Overall Heat Transfer Co-efficient, $U=300 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}$ (assume)

& $F_{corr}=0.86$

$$Q=U \times A_o \times \Delta T_{LM} \times F_{corr}$$

$$\text{or, } 1128.978 \times 10^3 = 300 \times A_o \times 22.41 \times 0.86$$

$$\text{or, } A_o = 195.26 \text{ m}^2$$

Tube Length, L :

$$A_o = \pi \times OD_t \times L \times N_t$$

$$\text{or, } 195.26 = \pi \times (25.4 \times 10^{-3}) \times L \times 650$$

$$\text{or, } \underline{L = 3.76 \text{ m}}$$

Tube Pitch Ratio, PR :

$$PR = \frac{PT}{OD}$$

$$= \frac{31.75}{25.4}$$

$$= 1.25$$

Tube Clearance, C :

$$\begin{aligned}C &= P_T - OD_t \\&= 31.75 - 25.4 \\&= 6.35 \text{ mm}\end{aligned}$$

Shell Inside Diameter, D_s:

$$\begin{aligned}D_s &= 0.637 \sqrt{(C_t/CTP) \times [(A_o(PR)^2 \times OD_t)/L]}^{1/2} \\&= 0.637 \times 1 \times [(195.26 \times (1.25)^2 \times 25.4 \times 10^{-3})/3.26]^{1/2} ; \left(\sqrt{\frac{CL}{CTP}} \approx 1 \right) \\&= 0.982 \text{ m} \\&\approx 1 \text{ m}\end{aligned}$$

Baffles spacing, B:

$$\begin{aligned}B &= 0.4 D_s \\&= (0.4 \times 1) \text{ m} \\&= 0.4 \text{ m}\end{aligned}$$

Number of Baffle, N_B:

$$\begin{aligned}N_B &= \frac{L}{B} - 1 \\&= \frac{3.76}{0.4} - 1 \\&= 8.4 \\&\approx 9\end{aligned}$$

Shell Cross Flow Area, A_s:

$$A_s = (D_s \times C \times B) / P_T$$

$$= \frac{1 \times 0.00635 \times 0.4}{0.03175}$$

$$= 0.08 \text{ m}^2$$

Equivalent Shell Diameter, D_{hs} :

$$D_{hs} = 4P_T^2 / (\pi \times OD_t) - OD_t$$

$$= \frac{4 \times (0.03175)^2}{\pi \times 0.0254} - 0.0254$$

$$= 0.0251 \text{ m}$$

TUBE:

$$V_t = 1.48 \text{ m s}^{-1} \text{ (assume)}$$

$$Re_t = \frac{\rho \times V \times (ID)}{\mu}$$

$$= \frac{683.605 \times 1.48 \times 0.02118}{0.3551 \times 10^{-3}}$$

$$= 60345.13$$

$$Nu_t = (h \times D_{ht}) / k = 0.023 \times Re_t^{0.8} \times Pr^n ; \text{ where } n=0.4$$

$$\text{or, } \frac{ht \times 0.02118}{0.11885} = 0.023 \times (60345.13)^{0.8} \times (4)^{0.4}$$

$$\text{or, } h_t = 1500.16 \text{ W/m}^2$$

SHELL:

$$V_s = 0.25 \text{ m s}^{-1} \text{ (assume)}$$

$$Re_s = (\rho D_{hs} V_s) / \mu$$

$$= \frac{796.57 \times 0.0251 \times 0.25}{1.22 \times 10^{-3}}$$

$$= 4097.11$$

$$Nu_s = 0.36 \times Re_s^{0.55} \times Pr^{1/3} = (h \times D_{ht}) / k$$

$$= 0.36 \times (4097.11)^{0.55} \times (15)^{1/3} = \frac{hs \times 0.0251}{0.13}$$

or, $h_s = 446.134 \text{ W/m}^2$

$$\frac{1}{U} = \frac{1}{ht} + \frac{1}{h_s} + 0.0002 + 0.0002$$

$$\text{or, } \frac{1}{U} = \frac{1}{1500.16} + \frac{1}{446.134} + 0.0002 + 0.0002$$

or, $U = 302.3 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}$

This satisfied our assumption.

Pressure Drop Calculation:

For shell:

$$f_s = e^{0.576 - 0.19 \ln(Re)}$$

$$= e^{0.576 - 0.19 \ln(4097.11)}$$

$$= 0.366$$

$$\Delta P_s = f_s (N_b + 1) \frac{D_s}{D_{hs}} \left(\frac{1}{2} \times \rho_s \times V_s^2 \right)$$

$$= 0.366 (9 + 1) \frac{1}{0.0251} \times \frac{1}{2} \times 796.57 \times 0.25^2$$

$$= 3.6 \text{ KPa} < \Delta P_{\text{allow}} (70 \text{ KPa})$$

For tube:

$$f_t = 0.184 \times Re^{-0.20}$$

$$= 0.184 \times (60345.13)^{-0.20}$$

$$= 0.02$$

$$\Delta P_t = N_p \left(f_t \frac{L}{IDt} + 4 \right) \left(\frac{1}{2} \times \rho_t \times V_t^2 \right)$$

$$= 8 \times \left(0.02 \times \frac{3.76}{0.02118} + 4 \right) \left(\frac{1}{2} \times 683.605 \times 1.48^2 \right)$$

$$= 45.23 \text{ KPa} < \Delta P_{\text{allow}} (50 \text{ KPa})$$

5 Economic Analysis

Cost Analysis of Shell and Tube Heat exchanger (Steel)

Iteration 1		Iteration 2	
Tube		Tube	
No of Tube	960	No of Tube	1030
Length (m)	3.048	Length (m)	3.658
Outer Diameter (m)	0.0254	Outer Diameter (m)	0.0254
Inner Diameter (m)	0.02118	Inner Diameter (m)	0.02118
Volume (m ³)	0.4517405	Volume (m ³)	0.5816795
Density (Kg/m ³)	8050	Density (Kg/m ³)	8050
Mass (ton)	3.63651102	Mass (ton)	4.68251997
Price (\$/ton)	40	Price (\$/ton)	40
Cost (\$)	145.460441	Cost (\$)	187.300799

Cost Analysis of Shell And Tube Heat Exchanger (Copper)

Iteration 1		Iteration 2	
Tube		Tube	
No of Tube	960	No of Tube	1030
Length (m)	3.048	Length (m)	3.658
Outer Diameter (m)	0.0254	Outer Diameter (m)	0.0254
Inner Diameter (m)	0.02118	Inner Diameter (m)	0.02118
Volume (m ³)	0.45174	Volume (m ³)	0.581679
Density (Kg/m ³)	8960	Density (Kg/m ³)	8960
Mass (ton)	4.047595	Mass (ton)	5.211848
Price (\$/ton)	50	Price (\$/ton)	50
Cost (\$)	202.3797	Cost (\$)	260.5924

Comparison (Steel Tube)

Iteration 1		Iteration 2	
Velocity (m/s)	0.18 (CF)	Velocity (m/s)	0.16 (CF)
Velocity (m/s)	1.48 (HF)	Velocity (m/s)	1.20 (HF)
Cost (\$)	145.460441	Cost (\$)	187.300799

We know that economic velocity for Octane is 1.55 to 3.34 m/s. From our many iterations, we got many different velocities that are very far from the economic velocity. Two iterations gave us velocity that is close to economic velocity. From them we can see that iteration 1 is the closest to economic velocity.

Again, from the cost analysis, it can be seen that iteration 2 requires more tube than iteration 1. So, cost increases approximately \$42, making iteration 1 a better choice.

6 Material Selection

From the cost reports presented above, we can see that copper costs us extra, therefore copper tube is not economic for our purpose. Steel tube does the exact same job for a much lower cost. So, it will be a better choice for us.

For our design of this particular shell and tube heat exchanger, we select steel as our tube material and shell material.

7 Design

For our given problem, we select 1" OD tubes (14BWG) on 1¼" square pitch (PT) with ID 0.834", tube length 3.048 m and total no of tubes is 960.

Shell diameter is 1.219 m.

Tube material is steel.

Shell material is steel.

Fig: Schematic Diagram of the Design

8 HTRI Reports

We used HTRI software for this project to counter check our manual calculations. The software generated reports are attached here. The first report is for iteration 1 and the second report is for the iteration 2.

Service of Unit		Item No.	
Type	AES	Orientation	Horizontal
Surf/Unit (Gross/Eff)		233.48 / 225.20 m ²	Shell/Unit 1
		Surf/Shell (Gross/Eff) 233.48 / 225.20 m ²	
		Connected In 1 Parallel 1 Series	

PERFORMANCE OF ONE UNIT

Fluid Allocation		Shell Side		Tube Side	
Fluid Name		Kerosene		n-octane	
Fluid Quantity, Total		kg/s 19.4401		27.8001	
Vapor (In/Out)		wt% 0.0		0.0	
Liquid		wt% 100.0		100.0	
Temperature (In/Out)		C 25.00		70.00	
Density		kg/m ³ 810.00		783.14	
Viscosity		mN-s/m ² 1.9200		0.5200	
Specific Heat		kJ/kg-C 2.0100		2.3608	
Thermal Conductivity		W/m-C 0.1450		0.1300	
Critical Pressure		kPa		kPa	
Inlet Pressure		kPa 400.006		400.006	
Velocity		m/s		m/s	
		0.18		1.48	
Pressure Drop, Allow/Calc		kPa 70.001		5.244	
				50.001	
Average Film Coefficient		W/m ² -K 665.28		1977.83	
Fouling Resistance (min)		m ² -K/W 0.000200		0.000200	
Heat Exchanged		1.1416 MegaWatts		MTD (Corrected) 17.1 C	
Transfer Rate, Service		296.80 W/m ² -K		Calculated 351.32 W/m ² -K	
				Clean 426.07 W/m ² -K	
				Overdesign 18.37 %	

CONSTRUCTION OF ONE SHELL

Sketch (Bundle/Nozzle Orientation)

		Shell Side		Tube Side	
Design Pressure		kPaG 1034.21		1034.21	
Design Temperature		C 70.00		70.00	
No Passes per Shell		1		8	
Flow Direction		Downward		Downward	
Connections Size & Rating	In mm	1 @ 128.194		1 @ 154.051	
	Out mm	1 @ 128.194		1 @ 154.051	
	Liq. Out mm	@		@	

Tube No.	960	OD	25.400 mm	Thk(Avg)	4.216 mm	Length	3.048 m	Pitch	31.750 mm	Layout	90
Tube Type	Plain		Material	CARBON STEEL			Pairs seal strips	3			
Shell ID	1219.20 mm		Kettle ID	mm			Passlane Seal Rod No.	5			
Cross Baffle Type	PERPEND. SINGLE-SEG.		%Cut (Diam)	20.00			Impingement Plate	Circular plate			
Spacing(c/c)	289.691 mm		Inlet	512.771 mm		No. of Crosspasses	9				
Rho-V2-Inlet Nozzle	2800.61 kg/m-s ²		Shell Entrance	1053.24		Shell Exit	864.34		kg/m-s ²		
			Bundle Entrance	123.06		Bundle Exit	202.06		kg/m-s ²		
Weight/Shell	12659.0		Filled with Water	16831.1		Bundle	7298.58		kg		

Notes:		Thermal Resistance, %		Velocities, m/s		Flow Fractions	
		Shell	52.81	Shellside	0.18	A	0.261
		Tube	26.59	Tubeside	1.48	B	0.432
		Fouling	17.54	Crossflow	0.31	C	0.054
		Metal	3.06	Window	0.23	E	0.211
						F	0.041

Service of Unit		Item No.	
Type	AES	Orientation	Horizontal
Surf/Unit (Gross/Eff) 329.83 / 319.27 m ²		Shell/Unit	1
		Surf/Shell (Gross/Eff) 329.83 / 319.27 m ²	

PERFORMANCE OF ONE UNIT

Fluid Allocation		Shell Side		Tube Side	
Fluid Name		Kerosene		n-octane	
Fluid Quantity, Total		19.4401		27.8001	
Vapor (In/Out)		0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Liquid		100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Temperature (In/Out)		25.00	50.00	70.00	50.00
Density		810.00	783.14	675.54	691.67
Viscosity		1.9200	0.5200	0.3204	0.3898
Specific Heat		2.0100	2.0720	2.3608	2.2852
Thermal Conductivity		0.1450	0.1300	0.1162	0.1215
Critical Pressure					
Inlet Pressure		400.006		400.006	
Velocity			0.16		1.20
Pressure Drop, Allow/Calc		70.001	6.066	50.001	38.055
Average Film Coefficient		622.83		1731.21	
Fouling Resistance (min)		0.000200		0.000200	
Heat Exchanged		1.1416	MegaWatts	MTD (Corrected)	17.1 C
Transfer Rate, Service		208.80	W/m ² -K	Calculated	327.15 W/m ² -K
				Clean	391.04 W/m ² -K
				Overdesign	56.68 %

CONSTRUCTION OF ONE SHELL
Sketch (Bundle/Nozzle Orientation)

		Shell Side	Tube Side
Design Pressure		1034.21	1034.21
Design Temperature		70.00	70.00
No Passes per Shell		1	8
Flow Direction		Downward	Downward
Connections Size & Rating	In mm	1 @ 128.194	1 @ 154.051
	Out mm	1 @ 128.194	1 @ 154.051
	Liq. Out mm	@	@

Tube No.	1130	OD	25.400	mm	Thk(Avg)	4.216	mm	Length	3.658	m	Pitch	31.750	mm	Layout	90
Tube Type		Plain		Material		CARBON STEEL		Pairs seal strips		4					
Shell ID		1320.80		Kettle ID		mm		Passlane Seal Rod No.		5					
Cross Baffle Type		PERPEND. SINGLE-SEG.		%Cut (Diam)		20.00		Impingement Plate		Circular plate					
Spacing(c/c)		293.093		mm		Inlet		502.677		mm		No. of Crosspasses		11	
Rho-V2-Inlet Nozzle		2800.61		kg/m-s ²		Shell Entrance		1825.51		kg/m-s ²		Shell Exit		1399.63	
				Bundle Entrance		161.73		kg/m-s ²		Bundle Exit		260.72		kg/m-s ²	
Weight/Shell		16814.7		Filled with Water		22403.8		Bundle		10234.9		kg			

Notes:		Thermal Resistance, %	Velocities, m/s	Flow Fractions			
		Shell	52.53	Shellside	0.16	A	0.273
		Tube	28.29	Tubeside	1.20	B	0.425
		Fouling	16.34	Crossflow	0.28	C	0.052
		Metal	2.85	Window	0.20	E	0.212
						F	0.038